

THE ROLE OF ENVIRONMENTAL FACTORS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF CHILDREN'S PULMONARY DISEASES

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ABSTRACT

Environmental pollution is one of the main factors that negatively affect children's health, especially in the development of respiratory diseases. The functional immaturity of children's bodies makes them highly sensitive to harmful substances in the atmosphere. Children living in ecologically unfavorable areas have a higher incidence and severity of pulmonary diseases.

Introduction

Environmental pollution is one of the main factors that negatively affect children's health, especially in the development of respiratory diseases. The functional immaturity of children's bodies makes them highly sensitive to harmful substances in the atmosphere. Children living in ecologically unfavorable areas have a higher incidence and severity of pulmonary diseases.

Research objective

Statistical assessment of the impact of environmental factors on the development of pulmonary diseases in children in regional conditions.

Materials and methods

During the study, a retrospective analysis of medical records of children under observation in pediatrics and pulmonology departments was conducted. Children were divided into ecologically unfavorable and relatively favorable zones according to their area of residence. Clinical diagnoses, frequency of recurrence of diseases and severity of course were compared. The results were evaluated in percentage terms.

Results and discussion

According to the results of the analysis, respiratory diseases were detected in 65–70% of cases in children living in ecologically unfavorable areas, while in relatively favorable ecological areas this figure was 40–45%. Recurrent bronchitis was recorded in 38% of cases in unfavorable areas, and in 21% in favorable areas. The incidence of obstructive bronchitis and bronchial asthma was 2 times higher, respectively, and bronchial asthma was found in 12–14% of children. The frequency of respiratory symptoms occurring more than 4 times a year was 56% in children living in unfavorable ecological areas. These results indicate that

the constant impact of environmental factors on the mucous membrane of the respiratory tract leads to the exacerbation of inflammatory processes.

Conclusions

Environmental factors play an important role in the development of pulmonary diseases in children, and the incidence and recurrence rates in unfavorable areas are significantly higher. It is necessary to strengthen preventive measures, improve environmental control, and regularly monitor children at risk.

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